

Modeling the Impacts of Altering the Power Generation Mix on the Climate, Land, Energy and Water (CLEWs) Nexus in Kenya

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of a Climate, Land, Energy, Water Systems (CLEWS) model analysis conducted to assess the impacts of resource reallocation on climate, land, energy and water systems in Kenya. Its framework was used to develop three scenarios, Baseline, Reduced Carbon Emissions (RCE), and Increased Renewable Energy (IRE), to assess their impacts in relation to sustainable development. The main findings of this study reveal that reduced thermal power generation results in a reduction in CO₂ emissions and cooling water demand, which allows more water to be reallocated for public supply and irrigation. Furthermore, an increase in renewable energy generation from solar and onshore wind results in increased capital costs and cost of power generation compared to the baseline scenario. Recommendations include increasing renewable energy generation using already predominant sources such as geothermal to minimize greenhouse gas emissions, deploying technologies needed to achieve climate goals, and managing resources by exploring options aimed at maximizing the benefits of available resources. Nevertheless, a successful implementation of the CLEWs model findings is contingent on constructive collaboration between implementing bodies such as government ministries and other stakeholders.

1. Introduction

Kenya has long been a continental leader in renewable energy use for electricity production, with the use of hydropower dating back a century. As a result of climate change impacts, water levels in various hydropower sites have been greatly reduced, leading to a major decline in electricity generation capacity. To meet this electricity deficit, Kenya uses thermal power production, which is expensive and contributes to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. As a signatory to the UNFCCC Paris Climate Change Agreement, it committed to contributing to global climate change mitigation and adaptation through its submission of the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) commitment to reduce these emissions by 32% by 2030.

This study investigates the impact of decommissioning thermal power plants and Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) usage in power generation and the deployment of increased capacities of solar and wind renewable energy sources with a focus on Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems (CLEWs). The purpose is to define and analyze the different scenarios to demonstrate how the changes in the energy mix will impact CLEWs. The scope of the study is to perform a comparative analysis of three scenarios using the CLEWs framework within the OSeMOSYS tool. The objective is to have a model that can quantify the impacts of eliminating thermal energy from the generation mix, and increasing the capacity of solar and wind energy to lead to a reduction in emissions from CO₂.

2. Methodology

This modelling research explored the integrated analysis of resource systems, interactions and quantitative assessment of critical linkages, the CLEWs through the use of Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OseMOSYS) tool. Although it was primarily developed for energy systems analysis, the tool's functionality and flexibility allow for its application to CLEWs. The focus of the CLEWs framework is analyzing interactions between the systems of climate, land, energy and water, supported by quantitative studies of interactions and the use of resources (Ramos et al., 2021).

The data from the CCG Starter Data Kit (SDK) for the Kenya Sand and Base file were applied to model the energy part. The land and water data were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and the International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

2.1 Scenarios

This modelling exercise sought to answer the following research question:

What are the effects of phasing out HFO usage and increasing Renewable Energy (RE) generation on Climate, Land, Energy and Water Systems (CLEWS)?

The research question was answered in the following in a two-pronged approach:

- a. the first scenario (RCE) assessed the impact of reduced HFO usage by gradually eliminating thermal power generation on CO₂ emissions and water demand.
- b. the second scenario (IRE) assessed the cost implications of increased solar and wind capacity in the country's power generation mix.

The three scenarios that were developed are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Scenario descriptions

Scenario	Description	Assumptions
Baseline	Current state of energy mix and emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Main power sources are hydro, geothermal, thermal, wind, biomass and solar
Reduced Carbon Emissions (RCE)	Reduced CO ₂ emissions due to phasing out of thermal power plants	Guideline: <i>achievement of NDCs</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">No new investments and gradual decommissioning of thermal power plants until a full phase-out in 2050

Increased Renewable Energy (IRE)	Increased renewable energy generation from solar and wind	Guideline: Kenya Energy Transition & Investment Plan 2023 – 2050 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased capacity of solar and wind resources to 8 GW and 14 GW by 2040
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3. Results

3.1 Baseline Scenario vs. Reduced Carbon Emissions (RCE) Scenario

In the RCE scenario, HFO will be phased out gradually by 2050, resulting in progressive emission reductions ranging from 16% in 2025 to 84% in 2045, as shown in Figure 1. While this scenario exhibits high potential to meet Kenya’s climate goals, the model revealed that achieving the NDC commitment by 2030 solely through changes in the energy mix is infeasible. However, the goal is achievable by 2050. Consequently, to remain aligned with the country’s commitment, it is necessary to increase emission abatement efforts through other avenues, such as the electrification of transport (e-mobility).

Figure 1: Reduced CO₂ emissions from phasing out thermal energy

Further, the switch from HFO resulted in a decrease in water demand for use in cooling thermal power plants, as shown in Figure 2. These water-intensive power generation plants pose a sizeable challenge in ensuring sufficient water supply for agriculture and public use. The need for economical water management is driven by high population growth rates and water demand, and decreased precipitation due to climate change.

Figure 2: Difference in water demand between the Baseline and RCE scenarios

3.2 Baseline vs. Increased Renewable Energy (IRE) Scenario

While the adoption of RE sources in favour of thermal energy sources is commendable, the ambitious targets laid out in the KETIP result in negative cost implications. Results from the modelling exercise showed a 33% increase in the cost of power generation in 2040. Similarly, a higher capital investment was required to ramp up solar and wind generation capacity in the lead-up to the 2040 target year. These findings are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Cost of power generation in the Baseline and IRE scenarios

Figure 4: Capital investment requirements in the Baseline and IRE scenarios

4. Discussion

The country's power generation mix in the baseline scenario is dominated by green sources, including hydro, geothermal, onshore wind, and solar. However, thermal energy generated from the combustion of Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) ranks as the second most-utilized source after hydro. Resultantly, HFO emerges as the main contributor to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the baseline. Phasing out thermal energy from Kenya's power generation mix is beneficial to the country. To begin with, the reduced CO₂ emissions greatly contribute to reducing the country's carbon footprint and securing its future against the disastrous effects of climate change. Additionally, since Kenya is a net-importing economy, the country stands to enjoy massive benefits from reducing its importation of petroleum products, whose prices are highly sensitive to geopolitical changes. Currently, the importation of petroleum products accounts for a quarter of Kenya's total import bill estimated at US\$ 4.5 billion. Considering the declining value of the shilling in recent months, foreign currency savings from reduced oil imports would be a welcome outcome in preserving the shilling's value as well as shoring up the Central Bank's forex reserves.

Besides that, the RCE scenario emphasized the need to adopt a multifaceted approach to meet Kenya's NDC commitment of decreasing emissions by 32% before 2030. Other avenues to reduce emissions include increasing tree cover from the current 6.2% to 10%, adopting more climate-resilient agricultural practices, increasing the adoption of electric mobility, and deploying high-efficiency demand-side technologies (Stockholm Environment Institute, 2017). This will involve inter-ministerial cooperation among various government agencies to coordinate climate action.

In 2023, Kenya unveiled the Kenya Energy Transition and Investment Plan 2023 – 2050 (KETIP) to guide the country's switch to cleaner energy. Some of KETIP's energy objectives are to increase the capacity of solar and wind energy from the current 0.41 GW and 0.436 GW to 8GW and 14 GW, respectively. This will see them play a larger role in the country's power generation mix, as illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 5: Difference in the contribution of solar and wind power in Kenya's energy mix in the Baseline and IRE scenarios

In the IRE scenario, the model illustrated the financial infeasibility of the KETIP regarding increasing solar and onshore wind power generation capacity. To counter this outcome, it is recommended to increase investment in already dominant renewable energy sources, prioritizing geothermal. Kenya is estimated to have up to 10,000 MW of untapped geothermal energy spanning 14 sites, enough energy to meet the country's demand five times over (EPRA, n.d.). Geothermal is preferred due to its stability since it does not depend on rain, wind or sun fluctuations. Policies aimed at stimulating the demand for electricity are critical to rationalizing the increased development of the country's geothermal resources

5. Conclusion

This study has explored the impacts of resource reallocation away from thermal energy and towards solar and wind capacity enhancement on the CLEWs nexus in Kenya. By analysing the three scenarios, Baseline, RCE and IRE, the study has provided insights into the potential implications of increasing renewables to gradually reduce the overreliance on thermal power plants for power generation in the country. The findings have also drawn special attention to the importance of increasing emissions abatement efforts to minimise GHG emissions and consequently achieve sustainability.

It is recommended that policymakers and stakeholders collaboratively evaluate the potential of increasing existing renewable energy technologies to minimize GHG emissions, deploy technologies needed to achieve climate goals and manage resources effectively by exploring options related to maximizing the benefits of available resources. Kenya's untapped geothermal potential holds the key to further greening the national grid while remaining within reasonable cost constraints encompassing capital investment and the cost of electricity generation.

Up-to-date data availability remains a challenge for quantitative modelling. In the future, there is a need to enhance data availability to improve the accuracy of models. In doing so, CLEWs model results will be a valuable tool for informing policy and investment decisions, prioritizing competing water uses, charting pathways to modernizing agriculture, and maintaining alignment with climate goals such as NDCs. For instance, in this case, the IRE scenario findings could form the rationale for further investment in geothermal energy compared to developing new solar and wind capacity. Additionally, there is limitless potential to integrate various energy modeling tools, such as CLEWs and the Energy Access Explorer, to quantify the risk of financial institutions seeking to fund agricultural projects in compliance with ESG goals.

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